

Comparative Study of Materialism in Contemporary Church and Yorùbá Religion: A Tool for National Integration in Nigerian Society

Bùsáyò Qláníyì ÒGÚNÀJÒ PhD

Department of Religions, Ikire Campus, Osun State University, Osogbo, Nigeria

boogunajo@gmail.com, busayo.ogunajo@uniosun.edu.ng

Abstract

The quest for materialism and its influence in Christianity and Yoruba religion has been a global discourse that attracts attention of the general public. It is designed to defraud and exploit the sick, poor, biblical illiterate Christians and ignorant adherents of Yorùbá religion. This paper therefore set out to examine its prevalent dimension in human practice of religion and the contributing factors induced by some modern religious leaders to the social and economic upheaval in the society. The research adopted a comparative study approach in analysing discussions towards discovering the causes of materialism. This study delved with the structural roots of materialism in Nigeria and discovered, amongst other things, that many materialistic religious leaders are driven by the love of money and not love for God, or the people. The study also discovered that part of the reasons for the prevalence of materialism are that verses, and passages of the scripture and Ifá Corpus are taken and quoted out of context for selfish reasons. The study concluded that materialistic message is the worst kind of materialism and deception which lays the foundation of national disintegration, greed and social discontent in contemporary Nigerian society.

Keywords: Church, Ifá, Materialism, Tension, Integration, Understanding.

Introduction

Materialism is the belief that possession of money and physical comforts are more important than spiritual values in life. It means the pursuit of wealth, luxury and sensual indulgence. Elsdon in his view stated that, “materialism is a result of the insecurity which pervades human existence, and which stems from human’s estrangement from God.”¹In contemporary society, materialism can be found in every sphere of human life, no matter what religious or social class that is examined. It has been a common issue addressed by various religions. Religions provide standards by which adherents are expected to live. Such yardstick usually stipulates a life of modesty and the need to emphasize the spiritual concerns over the material. Materialism remains a menace which the world-over have wrestled with and has generated considerable concern among scholars.

There is no gainsaying that there is decadence and low level of morality in contemporary Nigerian society. The traditional values have been eroded by unending thirst for materialism. The symptoms of this are found in the breakdown of societal discipline, political intolerance, religious crisis and national disintegration. Despite commendable efforts of some scholars about crave for materialism in contemporary society; it does not seem that efforts made to ameliorate the situation are having the desired effect hence the need to continue and intensify the need for moral revival in contemporary Nigerian society.

The menace of materialism in contemporary society has become so fertile that most religious leaders advocate prosperity as part of spiritual salvation. According to Nwadiolor & Umeanolue, it is an often repeated saying that as humans makes giant strides in science and technology, the tendency is to shift away from religion.²However, these days, due to economic hardship and political uncertainties in contemporary society, people appear to be more concerned about using religion to achieve material ambitions. This largely account for why people drift to religion despite secularism. To Dike, the greatest enemy of the church, which, incidentally, is also the greatest enemy of all humankind today, is our mindless quest for material things.³ The massive and uncurtail growth of materialistic gospel message in contemporary churches today has largely confirmed this view.

Materialistic preaching with its unapologetic emphasis on the acquisition of wealth at all costs and the shameful deceptions of the materialistic preachers with their open display of affluence have distorted the value systems of Christianity and *Yorùbá* religion in contemporary society. Achunike confirmed that “the flamboyance life of the prosperity preachers inspires avidity for money.”⁴ They always want to live big, that is why their churches are architectural wonders. The aim here is to attract people, particularly the rich class. In their bid to live large, they always make efforts to acquire the resources with which to live big. This is followed by employment of all sorts of tricks to get more funds.

This is further backed up with biblical quotations and pressures on the people to give more and more. The attitude of the various religious bodies towards material gain, as well as the rights of religious leaders to benefit materially from their adherents, are the thorniest issues in contemporary society, and points to the basic status and perceived interest. Unending thirst for materialism is said to be more deadly than HIV or AIDS because, those it attacks are seldom aware. There are also not enough doctors who can help, as most doctors are themselves helpless victims.⁵ Unfortunately, what is in large supply are purveyors of the virus who claim that, far from being a curse, material prosperity is in fact God’s special blessing for those who sing, dance and clap for Jesus, and who make bountiful sacrifices regularly to the Deity through intermediaries.

The focus of this paper is on the contemporary trend of Christianity and *Yorùbá* religion in Nigeria which is capitalised by the exchange of influence of materialism in the two religions. The task before this paper is to attempt a critical study of the issue of materialism in contemporary society. The paper examines reasons for prioritization of material possessions in Christianity and *Yorùbá* religion. This study will proffer ways Christians and *Yorùbá* religious adherents should relate with material things.

Contemporary Church and Materialism

The Old Testament (OT) scripture serves as background to the life and ministry of Christ. Christ in this stance, is the link between the OT and the New Testament (NT) because in him is the fulfilment of the OT messianic prophecies. Yahweh’s relationship with Israel was characterized by His insistence on obedience and righteous living, instead of selfishness and corruption based on materialism. The phenomenon of materialism as well as God’s warning against it is prevalent in the OT and NT accounts. A brief survey of some of these would be necessary. Abraham is considered as the genealogical father of the Israelite nation. His life and call showed the initial promise of God for Israel (Gen. 12:1-3) and remains a true model of God’s relationship with human. He was wealthy, “Abraham was very rich in cattle, in silver and in gold.” (Gen. 13:2), but despite his wealth, he remained Godly. This is a clear portrayal of the fact that, when God blesses with wealth, and if one maintains obedience and good relationship with Him, the spiritual and material life can be sustained.

Another prominent personage is Solomon, who was an epitome of God’s endowment of riches unto human. He was the richest and mostly blessed with both spiritual and material wealth. It remains evident from Solomon’s case that to be wealthy is not wrong but to abuse it is extremely wrong. Solomon failed in maintaining balance between his spirituality and wealth. He sustained the wealth through over-taxation and forced labour. He yielded to idols worship and cults of his numerous wives and concubines (1Kings 11:4). This clearly shows that if unmanaged, wealth can become an obstacle to righteous living. The Bible warns about luxury, prosperity and material wealth and the dangers associated with it are stressed repeatedly. The OT prophets focused especially on this theme. The use of wealth was a major topic of prophetic utterance, such that one does not make a deity of the provision of God. God can and does favour his people with wealth, but they must be very careful on various fronts. They must not let it become a snare to them, they must be generous with it, and must remember the source of such riches.

The picture of materialism changes slightly in the NT, which emphasizes the breakthrough of the kingdom of God in the coming of Jesus Christ. Here the negative side of money receives greater emphasis. Jesus spoke often about money in parables (Lk.12:19) and showed the folly of being materially rich but poor with God. He condemned the idolatrous attitude of treating money as a deity (mammon) (Lk.16:13). While it may seem that the

NT has strong words of exhortation and warning for the wealthy, we should not assume that material poverty has inherent value. Jesus and the apostles applauded the Christians in their efforts to alleviate suffering. God does not condemn anyone for having riches. Riches come to people from many sources, but He gives grave warnings to those who seek after them more than they seek after God and trust in them more than in God.

Materialism is the belief that money possessions and physical comforts are more important than spiritual values in life. There is a strong feeling among some contemporary Christians that materialism is a sin. Contemporary churches teach that the worship of things is a sincere idolatry. It has been emphasized in Christian songs and books that a genuine Christian cannot be materialistic. Call a believer materialist and you will meet with vocal protest. No one wants to be a materialist. No one believes that he is a materialist. Almost any Christian can repeat 1 Timothy 6:10a “The love of money is the root of all evil.” But do they really carry this out in practice? Most importantly, is the materialism that is condemned so loudly, the materialism that scripture warns against or a distorted ideology of human concoction?

Graig emphasized that, “It is very easy for Christians to say they are not materialist by defining materialism to mean something less than it is: the sin of acquiring unnecessary wealth.”⁶ In the light of this, it is easy for many Christians to become so accustomed to a lifestyle focused on worldly gain such that they can no longer see that they are caught in it. It is so normal to such people, that the suggestion of being materialistic seems absurd. They are so used to their comforts and the pursuit of wealth that they do not recognize it for what it is. It is altogether too easy to think that if Christians attend church regularly, hold the right doctrines, live otherwise righteous lives, and do not neglect the other duties of a church-going Christian that their focus is on the Lord, when their values and daily lives really centre on the world. But this is a big mistake. The more those material things and their acquisition, preservation, and disposal occupy them and consequently, out of hearts, the less room there is for God’s spirit to work in them and the more their joy as Christians is stolen by the world. Christ’s description, in the parable of the Sower (Luke 8), says that the cares of the world are like weeds that choke the word of God.

Materialistic gospel message tends to place more emphasis on the material prosperity of Christians than the gospel of eternal salvation of the soul. It is ironical that some men of God have gallantly deviated from the path and only pay lip service to the true essence of Christianity. The fact that church business remains one of the most flourishing businesses in contemporary society is openly embraced and flaunted in our faces without apologies. It is very common to hear people outside the churches, and other religious groups, comment on the venality of many pastors, most notably materialistic gospel preachers. One observer joked that, “Church is the biggest growing industry in the country.”⁷

There is no doubt that in some churches, the financial motive is moving men of God as much as the spirit is; and however cynical such comments may appear, there is a strong element of truth in them. While it may not be easy to explain why people continue to flock these materialistic preaching churches and give their money willingly. It is simplistic as well as patronizing, to assume, as such an approach would imply, that people are simply duped by clever and unscrupulous men. Clearly, people are making decisions to convert based on a real awareness of their needs and interests and needs that conversion serves them.

Churches today have become commercialized as a business venture. The establishment of churches is now the quickest way to get rich. According to Nmah, many people see church founding as the easiest way of beating down the biting economic crunch.⁸ Jowitt added that: “Criticism made of some churches include the fact that raising of funds enable some leaders to live in a decidedly elitist style; and some of the leaders preached a very materialistic gospel, so encouraging poorer members to believe that through their membership they would sooner join the rank of the rich.”⁹ The ignorant congregation are made to witness organized miracles and made to hope on promises of prosperity. The race for material wealth is actively influenced by these supposed men of God. Commenting on materialistic gospel preachers Fakoya said that “holiness in their preaching translates to wealth. You can only be holy if you are wealthy and powerful.”¹⁰ In order to continually give testimonies in churches,

men and women would do anything for money. No source of wealth is ever questioned by these materialistic gospel preachers.

There is obviously nothing wrong with seeking prosperity. However, there are many things wrong with striving to be rich at all costs to appear as the specially favoured of a material-minded God with the society remaining morally bankrupt for it. The lucrative nature of this contemporary pseudo-Christianity can only be explained by the rapid nature of its spread. It is particularly endearing to many people because of its tendencies to revert to traditional means in their efforts to perform miracles. Their flamboyance is another attractive feature as this is well attuned to the African psyche that loves all things pomp and gorgeous.

The root problem of materialism in the contemporary Christian churches has been traced partly to the change of emphasis on the pulpits from the cross to acquisition of the material possessions and miracles.¹¹ Most adherents have been experiencing abject poverty. The recent socio-economic situation of contemporary Nigeria has been a symptomatic of the endemic plurality of Nigeria's religious landscape. The country is now a procreant ground for all kinds of religious movements. Reason is because Nigerian economic development is too low and has made religion mainly to be seen in Nigeria as a source of economic benefit. So, church opening, and its enterprise have become a career to Nigerians and qualification certificate for lazy youths. Olorode observed that many people are looking beyond realities for the solution of their multifarious emotional and economic problems and religion has been their last resort.¹² Essien also noted that religion has become a top bracket business in Nigeria and the key players in this situation do not accept the economic reasons as the basis of their action.¹³ Rather they argue that their action is purely based on a spiritual dimension, which has proved not to be such. The mad craze for money has made some people willing to commercialize religion for their own benefit and interest. Many vulnerable people have fallen into the trap of this unholy merchandise.

Although the case of trading in God's name and using religion as a marketplace did not even begin from this century; it began even from the century of Jesus Christ. Jesus experienced this when he entered the temple at Jerusalem during his earthly ministry; he saw some people selling and buying in the house of his father, he was not happy with them and drove them out. However, the question is, is it possible to drive away all those materialistic gospel preachers that have commercialized religion for their own interest in order to gain from it? These gains are evident in their quest for property ownership in projects that include building of homes, hotels, guest houses, establishment of schools, water factories, publishing and selling of recorded cassettes of messages, prayers, counselling, performed miracles, testimonies, which they sell for them to have buoyant economy.

Yorùbá Religion and Materialism

The *Yorùbá* Religion and Ethics have concepts dealing with materialism. We have examined in the previous section, the Christian position which is an arm of our comparative study. In this section, we shall discuss the second part, which is *Yorùbá* religious and ethical basis for the concept of materialism by examining elements in *Yorùbá* Religion which served as basis for the people's attitude towards materialism. It remains vivid that virtually every sphere of life and beliefs of the people can be traced to religion. This agrees with Bolaji Idowu's conclusion that: "the real keynote of the life of the *Yorùbá* is neither in their noble ancestry nor in the deeds of their heroes. The keynote of their life is their religion. In all things, they are religious."¹⁴ This is an attestation to the fact that religion is fundamental to the conception of ethics of the *Yorùbá*. It is so pervasive that it encompasses all aspect of their lives. Many ethical values are rooted in the religion, which gives ethics its moral force. This is the basis of our study of the role of religion, in the search for a proper understanding of materialism among the *Yorùbá*.

Yorùbá religion and its many ethical values discourage materialism. This concept arises from the *Yorùbá* perception that this human world is not the perfect and final home of humans. They believe that human's true home is in heaven and his sojourn on earth is temporal and on a mission like a marketplace after which human's return to his heavenly home. Olajubu further clarified this belief in *Yorùbá* saying that:

Ayél'ojà, òrun nilé

*A díá fún Olódùmarè,
Bàbá atayémátu
Béèdélé ayé bẹ̀ẹ̀,
È ó jábò
Ohun tíẹ̀ rí.¹⁵*

Translation:

The world is a marketplace; heaven is home,
Ifá divination was performed for *Olódùmarè*, the sustainer of the
world.

If you get to the world, you will account when you return what
you have experienced.

Humans are pictured as being engaged in struggle to live their life in accordance to the dictates of the spiritual and the material. A person whose lifestyle is given to pursuing the acquisition of wealth and indulgent in the pleasures of this world is perceived as being worldly. Therefore, it is in this context of living in consciousness of heaven and the world that we shall examine the concept of materialism. In the same vein, the ethical is conceived in terms of human adherence to moral laws of the Supreme Being, while unethical conduct is identified with the system and characteristic vices of the world.

Priests occupy a pride of place in the religious life of the *Yorùbá*. They are the official servant of the divinity and mediator between God, divinity and humans. There are different priests in *Yorùbá* Religion; each divinity in *Yorùbá* land has his or her priesthood. One of the unique features of the *Yorùbá* priesthood is the caution against materialism. Bolaji Idowu wrote on the priest that: It is laid down that a *Babaláwo* must not abuse his office in any way; if he does, he will never be received into heaven. Therefore, no *Babaláwo* should use his position to enrich himself in any way; he must not refuse anybody his service on account of money.¹⁶ This is a clear control measure for the priest against the danger of materialism. Priest is expected to exhibit the ideals of the divinity he represents. This often involves a display of simple and modest lifestyle. However, there are various moral taboos that serve as checks to the actions of the priest as well as the worshippers.

In essence, materialism is regarded as not ideal for an effective priestly vocation. However, this sacred injunction is largely disregarded now that materialism is the order of the day. Therefore, the importance of training to *Yorùbá* religious priest is to formulate their character, instil the acts of communal service, and cultivate a modest lifestyle and to apply moderation to discourage materialistic tendencies. Priests are not expected to utilize their training to make money but should shun materialism. This section submitted that there is a correlation between priesthood in *Yorùbá* Religion and materialism in the society. Despite the above, there can be positive ways of employing spiritual powers to affect wealth. *Yorùbá* traditional priest could also produce portions for success in trade and general businesses. A typical example of such portion is *àwúre* (success medicine).¹⁷

Songs constitute a rich heritage of all *Yorùbá* and have been prominently used as a tool of fanning materialism. Singing is always a vehicle conveying certain sentiments or truth.¹⁸ It forms one of the most effective mediums of expressing the people's beliefs, doctrines and philosophy. *Yorùbá* songs are inspiring as they are loaded with facts and philosophical statements. The morals of the people are also deeply preserved and expressed in songs. There had been songs waxed to praise the wealth of prominent citizens. Such persons soon after becoming rich are at times conferred with chieftaincy titles in their communities. The motivation for such awards could be a subtle way of securing the rich person's material donations to the traditional rulers, institutions or communities.

However, it is rare for poor people, even if they are principled and intelligent, to be accorded such honours. There are, however, positive influences of *Yorùbá* songs. Usually, in *Yorùbá* traditional society, a person of shady character is not celebrated. It appears that, the adulation of crooks is a recent phenomenon. Prior to this, ethics was emphasized, and most songs were directed to teach people to cultivate good character and imbibe virtues such as hard work, chastity, contentment and modesty in lifestyle.¹⁹

Prayer is a very important element in worship among the *Yorùbá*, both formal and informal prayers are resorted to from time to time. The heart of prayer in *Yorùbá* Religion is petition. Poverty is seen in *Yorùbá* belief as an avoidable situation. It can be avoided through hard work, as well as the influence of one's destiny. The *Yorùbá* knows that hard work or ordinary human efforts alone may not automatically earn prosperity. One needs the co-operation of the supernatural. A crucial part of the daily prayer of *Yorùbá* religion adherents is for material well-being. This is because poverty is seen as a curse. Humans pray constantly for divine blessing in his profession or choice of trade. In fact, no business is ventured without prayers. Prayer for material success can come in form of simple supplication or petition. Often, it assumes the forms of commands using the power of spoken words after set patterns of rituals. The most common of these is incantation, which is believed to be efficacious to accomplish the desired goal. A relevant incantation here is that of *àwúre* (for goodness). It goes thus.

Ifá owó, ifáomọ
Ifá ohun rere gbogbo
Kó má dàwá sódò mi o
Kít'ẹrú t'omọ máa f'owó ọwọ wọn fún mi o
B'ẹyẹlé bájí
Ẹyẹlé áf'àpò f'are owó wọlé
*Emi náà lóní ẹnare tẹmi sími.*²⁰

Translation:

Goodluck of money, good luck of children, good luck of every good thing,

May you all rush unto me! Let everyone give me the money in their hands!

If the pigeon wakes up the pigeon will draw blessing of money into the house

I too say present my blessing to me.

Another example is as follows.

Ẹta kánkán, ẹ ta wàrà
Ẹlọ rẹẹ mowó fún mi wá
Igún lóní kíwón ó f'owóolé wọn gún mi lówó
*Àkàlà lóní kí n rẹẹ wọlé wọn kàa.*²¹

Translation:

Hurry up, be hasty
Go to bring money for me
It is the vulture that says
They should touch my hand with their money
It is the *àkàlà* bird that says I should get the money
in their houses to count as mine.

The main desire of the enchanter of the above incantation is for money, albeit employing supernatural means. Although many people say such prayers, the fact remains that hard work and wisdom are needed to achieve true and legal riches. The consequences of such esoterically obtained riches can be dire at times. What we wish to emphasize here is the fact that the *Yorùbá* employ religion as a means of material possession. In essence, the supernatural is employed as an agent for seeking material blessings. Therefore, the *Yorùbá*, through their concept of prayer, do attach spiritual importance to material acquisition. Where this is often abused and misused, is if such prayers are rendered without the commensurate living of a good spiritual life. In that case, religion would be a mere tool for exploitation. There is nothing wrong in praying for wealth. What the *Yorùbá* discourage and cautious about is corrupt wealth and misuse of it.

There is a moral dimension to acquisition of wealth. Human beings have the common tendency to struggle in order to become rich through ways and means, which are immoral and exploitative. *Yorùbá* moral philosophy warns against getting rich through foul means:

Èké síse kòpé á mọ́ lówó
Ilẹ́ dídà kòpé á mọ́ dàgbà
*Ọjọ àti sùn lẹbọ.*²²

Translation:

Deceit may not prevent our getting rich,
Treachery may not prevent our longevity
The day of death is the crucial matter.

The *Yorùbá* strongly believes that one's eternity is paramount than material possession.

Adebambo in her philosophical compilation expresses the right use of material acquisitions for the good of humankind in the following rendition.

Bímo bá lówó
Kí n fowó ọ́hún sehun're
Kí n fowó ọ́hún mẹbí mọ̀rẹ́
Kí n fí sohun iyì l'ódèdè
K'ówó ọ́hún má wó mi mọ̀lẹ́ o jàre
Kó jẹ́ kín má jẹni rere síbẹ síbẹ
Nítorí bí enìyàn bá lówó lówó
Bí kò nìyì
Bí kò sìjẹ ẹni rere
Owó asán lóní
Owó irú wọn ti dèèwò
Ámọ́ á ro wọn nínú
Bó pé tíí irú owó bèẹ́ á dètẹ
Á wá daá pọn f'ólówó gan-an
Bí mo bá lówó
*Èmi ó f'owó sehun're láyé mi.*²³

Translation:

If I am rich in money
May I use the money to do well
May I use it for the good of relatives and friends
May I use it for the benefit of my community
May the money not fall me down
May it make me a good person still
Because if a person has money and has no goodwill
And he is not a good person
His money is futile
Such money becomes a boil
This will torment their bodies internally
After some time, such money becomes leprosy
And will become a problem for the owner
If I am rich in money
I will use the money
To do well in my life.²⁴

The above ethical philosophy contains realistic facts of life. The wrong use of money results in sorrow while the right use of it brings blessings, comfort and happiness. Such teachings as this are capable of influencing people to shun materialism and pursue positive use of wealth.

The ultimate lesson against materialism is the fact that it has no lasting benefit in the hereafter. Death is an inevitable experience, which puts an end to life's businesses, including material pursuit and acquisition.

Aìyè lojà, òrun nilé
Bí a bá kú láyé
A ó rọrun rẹé sin mìn
Asìkò laò mò
Kò sèni t'íkú kòlè kàn
Ikú tó p'otòsì
Ló mú'sẹẹ rẹ tán
Ikú tó p'olówó
*Ló k'owó b'ọmi.*²⁵

Translation:

The world is like a market, heave is home
If we die in the world
We go to heaven to rest
The timing is what we do not know
There is no one that will not die
The death that kills a poor man
Brought an end to his suffering
The death that kills the rich man
Makes nonsense of his money.

In the above quoted poetry, the thrust of the message is *Yorùbá* theology of the preference of spiritual things to material things. It succinctly stresses the futility of the material in view of the inevitability of death and the effect of material acquisition thereafter for the dead. This has been the central thesis of our research.

The *Yorùbá* moral values related to materialism have been operative and are still relevant in the life and religious philosophy of the people. Unfortunately, contemporary society has placed too much emphasis on western education and its curricula. This keeps students out of regular contact with the philosophical and moral values in the study of *Yorùbá* language and literature. Such emphasis on science education and western-oriented knowledge should not be to the detriment of the indigenous values of the *Yorùbá* people. It should target a balance between science and humanity for the benefit of humankind. This needs to be corrected if the rich moral values and traditions of the *Yorùbá* are to be sustained.

A critical look at the contemporary society easily suggests a gradual disappearance of *Yorùbá* religious values. People moan and grieve about the emerging morally decadent age. From the traditional rulers, religious leaders, parents, to political leaders, we keep lamenting over the emerging atrocities of this age. Our world has been variously described by many experts as the most hostile world. Others described it as a very wicked world, a perilous world and wicked generation.²⁶ Moral decadence remains prevalent, and the future seems to be bleak as a result of its attendant national disintegration.

Comparative Analysis of Materialism in Contemporary Church and Yorùbá Religion

This study has examined from a comparative approach, the concept of materialism in Contemporary Church and *Yorùbá* Religion based on the theological and ethical framework of both religions. This study attempts to de-escalate tension brought by misconception of the concept of materialism in the two religions with a view to integrate and improve adequate understanding via a comparative analysis of the concept in the two religions, after which contributions to knowledge in the area of this study shall be presented.

There is a religious ground for comparing the teachings of Christianity and *Yorùbá* Religion. The two are based on the concept of God and His influence over human life and beliefs. There is a dual operation of the spiritual and the physical in human life. The physical is usually dictated by material pursuits and desire whereas the spiritual requires renunciation (to a certain degree) of material indulgence. Although, material things such as money and wealth are not in themselves evil, rather, it is the undue love of, or attention given to them that create impediments to human spiritual life. A person that will grow spiritually is often required to eschew materialism.

For both Christians and adherents of *Yorùbá* Religion, their respective faiths have practical effects on their behaviours. The teachings therefore are not mere concept but practical guides to living, which influence many people who adopt them. In other words, the teachings on materialism are ethical codes in Christianity and moral values in *Yorùbá* Religion. They are taught as injunctions, not abstract philosophical concepts.

Christianity and *Yorùbá* Religion have common grounds in the use of proverbs and philosophical sayings, which influence human behaviours. There are numerous wisdom materials or proverbs in both. For Christianity, such parables are embedded in the Old Testament antecedent, the books of Proverbs, Ecclesiastes and the parables in the teachings of Jesus. *Yorùbá* Religion (which broadly encompasses the total life and belief of the people) also has an enviable array of parables and philosophical sayings, some of which were presented earlier, related to materialism. The average *Yorùbá* elder is marked by his ability to relate and deliver parables (*òwe*). Proverbs convey deeper messages and stick more in memory than ordinary words or statements because of the inherent or implied logic and graphic illustrations. A short witty proverb makes more sense at times than a long speech.

There is a common perception by the two faiths that material possessions in themselves are good and desirable. In fact, both religions see it as blessing from God having been created by God for human use. Poverty was commonly viewed as the un-ideal state for humans, a situation which no one wants experience. Poverty is seen as an inevitable state of the unfortunate and the lazy. What is commonly discouraged is the overemphasis of the material consciousness at the peril of spiritual goal and discipline. It is commonly taught that Godliness must govern the use of material wealth, which is God-given.

Hannah's song in 1 Sam. 2: 7-8 suggests that predestination is a factor for human material endowment.

The lord makes poor and makes rich; he brings low and lifts. He
rises the poor out of the dust and lifts the beggar from the dunghill
to set them among princes...

Although God's supreme will can make one rich, but human's input is necessary. Any human who is not hard working would not be expected to become rich.

In the same sense as above, *Yorùbá* Religion upholds the belief in predestination (through *áyànmó*, *àkúnlèyán* and *àdáyébá*) as a factor which divinely determines human position as being either rich or poor. We do not share a fatalistic interpretation of this belief. Our opinion as stated earlier, is that even though God's supreme will can determine human's position in life to a large extent, one's state is also determined by one's actions and beliefs. Therefore, the two religions advocate hard work. Even where God is taken as being responsible for adverse conditions, such conditions can be remedied through prayer with faith, as Jesus taught, or through prayer and appropriate sacrifices as taught in *Yorùbá* Religion.

God's material blessing differs in characteristics and duration than riches acquired through ungodly means. Proverbs 10:22 states that, "the blessing of the Lord, it makes rich, and he adds no sorrow with it." *Yorùbá* Religion agrees that the blessings from God are perfect in nature. This implies there are riches which are not from God but from satanic forces. The two religions believe there are evil entities that can also provide material endowments to people, ostensibly to ultimately deceive them from benefiting from God's ultimate spiritual blessings. Jesus taught on Mammon being the god of materialism and warned "you cannot serve God and Mammon" (Matt. 6:24).

Both Christianity and *Yorùbá* Religion discourage greed, stealing and corruption in general, being partly products of materialism. This is conveyed through direct teachings, parables and injunctions. Materialism is responsible for socio-economic exploitation of the masses by the privileged few in advantageous positions of

power in contemporary society. Governance in contemporary society is characterized by corruption, bribery, political instability and injustice.

Contentment with godliness is a virtue commonly advocated by the two faiths. They condemn vain lifestyle by people. Jesus taught the parable of the prodigal son who squandered the wealth of his father but had to return home into the forgiving arms of his loving father. In the same sense is a materialistic person prodigal. It is commonly upheld by the two faiths that peaceful and modest living is preferred to a false life of vain possessions.

The priestly vocation requires a reasonable degree of renunciation of material indulgence. As a group of people set aside unto spiritual services, materialism is considered a distraction from the religious goal of a priest. The same applies to discipleship training in Christianity. Both the teaching of Jesus Christ and *Yorùbá* Religion stipulate such material renunciations as prerequisite to effective priestly vocation. Apostle Paul in his pastoral epistle to Timothy, for instance, stipulated that a person, who would become bishop, must not be greedy or materialistic (1Tim. 3:3).

There are some basic differences between Christianity and *Yorùbá* Religion on the concepts of materialism. While Christianity is more distinct on the difference between the spiritual and the material, especially in respect to life in the hereafter; *Yorùbá* Religion is unclear. Not that it lacks a clear concept of the hereafter, but it does not strongly tie anti-materialism to it. To Christianity, the vanity of materialism is most exposed through its irrelevance in the hereafter, which is dominantly spiritual, in other words, material acquisitions on earth are of no consequences to the dead. On the other hand, *Yorùbá* Religion believes that there is a state of existence, attainable by human beings, beyond the limits of our present mortal lifespan. That there is continuation in existence after death is attested to by the beliefs, actions and practices of living people such as ancestor veneration and re-incarnation. The Christian “heaven” is more elaborately defined than the *Yorùbá* *Òrun rere* (good heaven).

The spiritual perception of materialism is due largely to the concept of salvation. Human strives to prevent material consciousness and indulgence from debarring his salvation in the hereafter. The concepts of salvation exist in both religions but have different contents. In Christianity the figure of the saviour and medium of this salvation is clearly defined but in *Yorùbá* Religion, there is no singular acclaimed figure of a saviour. However, there are clear prescriptions on how salvation (well-being) may be attained.²⁵

The opposite of living a materialistic life is the reliance on divine providence. God is benevolent to humankind. Christianity upholds the belief that God answers prayers made in faith and still provide for human multifarious needs. The miracles of God through divine providence are common in the Bible. For example, ask and it will be given unto you, seek and you will find, Knock and it will be opened to you (Matt. 7:7).

In *Yorùbá* Religion, divine providence, though acknowledged, is not emphasized. Rather, predestination is stressed. Caution against materialism is because one’s *Orí* (personality soul) may determine the course of one’s life, and one should therefore work hard and placate the *Orí* for a right direction of the destiny. Emphasis is not on prayer of faith as Jesus taught; rather it is performing the appropriate rituals and sacrifices, accompanied by right invocations. The case of the *àwúre* (charm of good luck) is an example of employing magic to engender goodwill.

Jesus Christ taught that material possessions of the rich can become a destructive force that can cost them the kingdom of heaven. He remarked after his encounter with the rich young ruler that it is easier for the camel to enter the eye of a needle than for a rich man to enter the kingdom of heaven. Riches in themselves are not condemned; in fact, they are desirable and encouraged if used in Godly ways. It is materialism that makes riches dangerous to the soul; such a perception of materialism vis-à-vis the salvific impact is not pronounced in *Yorùbá* Religion. Rather it is viewed as capable of being misused leading to immoral behaviour, that is, making the person unfit to be classified as *Omólúàbí*.

Whereas in Christ teachings, money is a consequence of spiritual good-standing “seek ye first the kingdom of God and its righteousness and all other things shall be added unto you” (Matt. 6:33) this is not so in *Yorùbá*

Religion. Money is the starting point for other blessings as Wande (1975), had sated in an *Odu* that money is first desirable and later it begets marriage, then children, good life and long life.

Conclusion

The foregoing comparisons show that there are areas of fundamental similarities and differences on the perception of materialism which must be embraced for national integration between the teachings and tenets of Christianity and *Yorùbá* Religion. This way, it has been shown that the study of religion in contemporary context brings challenges of a more effective and impactful practice by the adherents. It also shows that both Christian and *Yorùbá* religious norms can be used to affect a good ethical conduct in humanity in respect of addressing the menace of materialism to foster national integration.

This study has been able to establish linkage between Christian and *Yorùbá* Religion in the area of theology and ethics on materialism. It shows the relevance and relationship of both in addressing this common problem which runs counter to the spirituality of any given religion. Not only has the fundamental negative implications of materialism on spirituality and of societal morals at large been highlighted, the need for a collaborative effort by both religions has been advocated in the quest for a new orientation to people on the ethical imperatives related to spiritual living devoid of materialism. In this regard, a call for contemporary Christians to appreciate the relevance and efficacy of *Yorùbá* Religious ethics and norms which are complementary to Christian ethics is recommended.

Endnotes

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